

Nonlinear Control of Swing-Up Inverted Pendulum

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Abstract

This paper presents plant modeling, analysis, and nonlinear control design and implementation for swing-up, pendulum regulation, and arm tracking of the rotational inverted pendulum plant in Fig. 1. For the ideal case, the equilibrium states are characterized. It is shown, for example, that the pendulum cannot be kept at a fixed angle above the horizontal except in a vertical position. The control design centers on the pendulum regulation and arm tracking controllers. A sliding mode and a variable-gain PID controllers are chosen for regulation and tracking. Due to the strong coupling of the arm and pendulum dynamics, a 2DOF control configuration was used. A simple technique was used to swing-up the pendulum to within the region of attraction of the regulation controller. Results of computer simulations and laboratory photos are presented.

1. Introduction

Underactuated mechanical systems are those possessing more degrees of freedom than actuators. They can be useful, for example, in space applications where the total weight and power requirements of a system are critical design factors. Also, reducing the number of actuators can increase system reliability by reducing the number of components.

This paper presents the analysis, design and implementation of a nonlinear controller for an inverted pendulum plant. Figure 1 presents a diagram of the plant. It consists of a pendulum hinged at the end of a horizontal link (or arm) which is directly connected to the shaft of an electric motor. This plant has one control input (the motor torque) and two degrees of freedom (the arm and pendulum rotations). The control problems considered here are the swing-up of the pendulum from the downward position and the control of the arm and pendulum to follow desired trajectories. In the ideal case, the feasible equilibrium states were also characterized. Notice that the dynamics of this plant are different than those of the inverted pendulum on a linear track due to the effect of the rotating arm.

Various studies have considered the swing-up problem, among them see Furuta et al [1], Spong [2], Mori et al [3], Woklund [4]. These references use some type of

strategy to swing the pendulum up to within a predetermined range of the upward position (e.g., bang-bang state feedback; partial feedback linearization; precomputed, time optimal, bang-bang control; or a control law based on energy considerations) and then switch to a linear control law for regulation. The analyses in those studies are focused on finding swing-up controllers, and the design of a regulation controller is secondary.

The emphasis of the present paper is different. A regulation controller is designed with a sufficiently large region of attraction, so that a simple technique can be used to swing the pendulum up. The design procedure first focuses on analyzing the plant and designing a good regulation and tracking controller. After this is accomplished, an intuitive control technique is used to bring the pendulum within the region of attraction of the regulation controller.

The paper is organized in the following manner. First, an ideal model of the plant is presented. This is followed by an enhanced model that more accurately matches the response of the real plant in the laboratory. The design of the controller is next. The regulation, tracking and swing-up controllers are discussed and simulation results are presented. Finally, some details of the implementation are included and some laboratory results are presented.

2. Model of the Plant

This section presents the dynamic equations that describe the inverted pendulum plant. An ideal model is

presented first, followed by a laboratory model which includes additional dynamics and nonlinear terms.

Ideal Model

The ideal model was derived using the Euler-Lagrange equation. For simplicity, the motor dynamics are not included in the ideal model. The ideal dynamic equations are:

$$A\ddot{\theta} + B\ddot{\phi} + C = \tau \quad (1)$$

$$D\ddot{\theta} + E\ddot{\phi} + F + G = 0 \quad (2)$$

where:

$$A = J_1 + mL_1^2 + \frac{1}{4}mL_2^2 \sin^2(\phi),$$

$$B = \frac{1}{2}mL_1L_2 \cos(\phi),$$

$$C = -\frac{1}{2}mL_1L_2 \sin(\phi)(\dot{\phi})^2 + \frac{1}{4}mL_2^2 \sin(2\phi)(\dot{\phi}\dot{\theta}),$$

$$E = J_2 + \frac{1}{4}mL_2^2,$$

$$F = -\frac{1}{8}mL_2^2 \sin(2\phi)(\dot{\theta})^2,$$

$$G = -\frac{1}{2}mgL_2 \sin(\phi).$$

The variables are: ϕ =pendulum angle with respect to the vertical pointing up position (see Fig. 1), θ =arm angle with respect to a reference position (see Fig. 1), m =pendulum mass, J_1 =moment of inertia of the shaft and arm with respect to the shaft's main axis, J_2 =pendulum's moment of inertia with respect to its center of mass, L_1 =length of the arm, L_2 =length of the pendulum, g =gravitational acceleration, and τ =input torque (see Fig. 1). Equations (1) and (2) can also be combined to solve for $\ddot{\phi}$ and $\ddot{\theta}$:

$$\ddot{\phi} = \bar{H} + \bar{L}\tau \quad (3)$$

$$\ddot{\theta} = \bar{Q} + \bar{R}\tau \quad (4)$$

where:

$$\bar{H} = \frac{-[A(F+G) - CD]}{AE - BD}, \quad \bar{L} = \frac{-D}{AE - BD}$$

$$\bar{Q} = \frac{B(F+G) - CE}{AE - BD}, \quad \bar{R} = \frac{E}{AE - BD}$$

Note that the arm dynamics interact with the pendulum dynamics in two ways: by direct coupling of the arm's acceleration (D), and by the centrifugal force generated by the arm's angular speed (F). Direct coupling is the main mechanism used to control the pendulum dynamics. Because the coupling factor D goes to zero as the pendulum approaches the horizontal position ($\phi \approx \pm 90^\circ$), control through direct coupling when the pendulum is in this region is impossible (infinite input torque is required).

An interesting result comes from the effect of the centrifugal force acting on the pendulum, F . This force can be decomposed into two components: one acting along the length of the arm and the other acting on the same plane where the pendulum is moving (see Fig 2). This second component tends to push the pendulum toward the horizontal position whenever the arm is moving ($\dot{\theta} \neq 0$). For the ideal model, this implies that

the centrifugal force F will make it impossible to hold the pendulum indefinitely at a nonzero angle with a finite input torque.

Consider trying to hold the pendulum at a nonzero angle above the horizontal, i.e., $0^\circ < |\phi| < 90^\circ$. Since ϕ is constant, then $\dot{\phi} = \ddot{\phi} = 0$ and $C = 0$. From (3):

$$\tau = \frac{-\bar{H}}{\bar{L}} = \frac{-A(F+G)}{D} \quad (5)$$

which is proportional to $\dot{\theta}^2$. From equations (4) and (5), the arm's angular acceleration is:

$$\ddot{\theta} = \bar{Q} + \bar{R} \left[\frac{-A(F+G)}{D} \right] = \frac{-(F+G)}{D} \quad (6)$$

Equation (6) can be used to determine $\dot{\theta}$. Note that $F+G$ is not zero since both the gravitational and centrifugal forces torque the pendulum in the same direction away from the vertical position (see Fig. 2). Assuming zero initial arm speed, $\dot{\theta}$ is:

$$\dot{\theta} = \sqrt{\frac{2g \sec(\phi)}{L_2}} \tan \left[\sqrt{\frac{gL_2 \sin(\phi) \tan(\phi)}{2L_1^2}} t \right]$$

Since the arm speed goes to infinity in a finite time given by:

$$t_{\text{escape}} = \frac{\pi/2}{\sqrt{\frac{gL_2 \sin(\phi) \tan(\phi)}{2L_1^2}}}$$

the input torque necessary to maintain a constant pendulum position goes to infinity for $0^\circ < |\phi| < 90^\circ$. Hence, it is impossible to hold the pendulum indefinitely at a fixed position above the horizontal.

Now, consider the case of trying to position the pendulum at a constant angle below the horizontal, i.e., $90^\circ < |\phi| \leq 180^\circ$. Equation (3) applies here also.

However, in this range of ϕ the centrifugal force F pushes the pendulum up toward the horizontal position, while the gravitational force G pulls the pendulum down toward the vertical position. An equilibrium exists

when $F = -G$. From (5), $\tau = 0$ when this happens. The angular speed of the arm necessary to achieve equilibrium is given by:

$$F = -G \Rightarrow \dot{\theta} = 2\sqrt{\frac{-g \sec(\phi)}{2L_2}} \quad (7)$$

The minimum angular arm speed for which equilibrium is possible is:

$$\dot{\theta}_{\min} = 2\sqrt{\frac{g}{2L_2}} \quad (8)$$

This can be called the *Critical Arm Speed for Zero-Torque Pendulum Position Control*. Below this arm speed an input torque is necessary to maintain a constant pendulum angle below the horizontal. This input torque becomes smaller as the arm's angular speed increases, until it reaches zero at the critical arm speed (8). From that point on the pendulum angle can be controlled by appropriate control of the arm speed $\dot{\theta}$ using (7) to map $\phi^{\text{desired}} \rightarrow \dot{\theta}^{\text{required}}$.

Laboratory Plant Model

A model of the laboratory plant was developed starting from the ideal model. This model leads to computer simulations that more accurately match the response of the real plant, leading to better analysis and design. This model includes the motor dynamics, friction, and some hard nonlinearities. The following equations replace (1) and (2) in the laboratory model:

$$A_e \ddot{\theta} + B_e \dot{\phi} + C_e = T_d \quad (9)$$

$$D_e \ddot{\theta} + E_e \dot{\phi} + F_e + G_e + H_e = 0 \quad (10)$$

where $A_e = A + J_m$, $C_e = C + a_m \dot{\theta}$, $H_e = \frac{1}{2} b_p \dot{\phi}$, and $B_e = D_e = B = D$, $E_e = E$, $F_e = F$, $G_e = G$. Here, T_d is the torque developed by the motor; J_m is the rotational inertia of the rotor, and a_m and b_p are viscous friction terms.

In addition, some hard nonlinearities were included: input torque saturation $T_{d, \max}$, motor angular speed saturation $\dot{\theta}_{d, \max}$, static and dynamic motor friction T_{static} and T_{dynamic} , and input torque dead-zone $T_{d, \text{dead}}$. Scaling factors (dA_e , dB_e , dC_e , dD_e , dE_e , dF_e , dG_e , and dH_e) were used to tune the response of the model. Table 1 lists the parameters of the laboratory plant model.

3. Controller Design

The controller chosen has two main sections: the swing-up controller, and the positioning controller. The swing-up controller does its work by continuously increasing the pendulum speed until it reaches the region of attraction of the positioning controller. The positioning controller has the structure shown in Fig. 3. This structure has a regulation inner-loop that uses a sliding-mode controller. On the outer-loop, arm control is achieved by specifying a desired pendulum trajectory.

Table 1: Parameters of Laboratory Plant Model

Parameter	Value	Parameter	Value
J_1	0.04699 kg•m ²	T_{static}	0.10 N•m
J_2	0.00780 kg•m ²	T_{dynamic}	0.08 N•m
J_m	0.03790 kg•m ²	$T_{d, \text{dead}}$	0.147 N•m
L_1	0.36 m	dA_e	1.2
L_2	0.28 m	dB_e	1.12
m	1.1564 kg	dC_e	1.05
g	9.8 m•s ⁻²	dD_e	1.12
a_m	0.01932 N•m•s	dE_e	0.98
b_p	0.01 N•m•s	dF_e	1.00
$T_{d, \max}$	9.8 N•m	dG_e	1.08
$\dot{\theta}_{d, \max}$	28.27 rad/s	dH_e	5.5

Fig. 3: Structure of Positioning Controller

Dynamic Plant Model in Control Algorithm

The dynamic model used to derive the equations for the positioning controller was the same as the ideal model, but simplified to include only the most important terms. (11) and (12) are the simplified plant model equations used in the control laws:

$$\ddot{\phi} = \bar{H}_a + \bar{L}_a T_d \quad (11)$$

$$\ddot{\theta} = \bar{Q}_a + \bar{R}_a T_d \quad (12)$$

where:

$$\bar{H}_a = \frac{-[A_a(F_a + G_a)]}{A_a E_a - B_a D_a}, \quad \bar{L}_a = \frac{-D_a}{A_a E_a - B_a D_a},$$

$$\bar{Q}_a = \frac{B_a(F_a + G_a)}{A_a E_a - B_a D_a}, \quad \bar{R}_a = \frac{E_a}{A_a E_a - B_a D_a},$$

$$A_a = J_1 + mL_1^2, \quad B_a = \frac{1}{2} mL_1 L_2,$$

$$C_a = 0, \quad D_a = \frac{1}{2} mL_1 L_2, \quad E_a = J_2 + \frac{1}{4} mL_2^2,$$

$$F_a = -\frac{1}{4} mL_2^2 \phi(\dot{\theta})^2, \quad G_a = -\frac{1}{2} mgL_2 \phi.$$

The centrifugal force acting on the pendulum was included because it helps to improve the response of the control system. Note that T_d replaces τ in this model because the controlled input is T_d , not τ . Scaling factors were used to approximate the response of this simplified model to the response of the laboratory plant model in Section 2. Table 2 presents the scaling factors.

Table 2: Scaling Factors for Simplified Plant Model

Parameter	Value	Parameter	Value
dA _a	1.35	dE _a	0.98
dB _a	1.00	dF _a	1.05
dC _a	0.00	dG _a	1.00
dD _a	1.00	dL _a	1.05

Pendulum Controller

The pendulum is controlled by a sliding-mode controller using the theory as presented in Slotine and Li [5]. The sliding surface chosen was:

$$s = \left(\frac{d}{dt} + \lambda \right)^2 \left(\int_0^t \tilde{\phi} dt \right) = \dot{\tilde{\phi}} + 2\lambda\tilde{\phi} + \lambda^2 \int_0^t \tilde{\phi} dt$$

where $\tilde{\phi} = \phi - \phi_{des}$ is the tracking error and ϕ_{des} is the desired pendulum position. Using this sliding surface, the sliding control law is:

$$T_d = \left[\frac{-\bar{H}_a + V + W}{\bar{L}_a} \right] \quad (13)$$

where:

$$v = \ddot{\phi}_{des} - 2\lambda\dot{\tilde{\phi}} - \lambda^2\tilde{\phi} \quad (14)$$

$$w = -K \text{sat} \left(\frac{s}{\Phi} \right) \quad (15)$$

(13) is an Input-Output feedback linearization term with ϕ as the output and T_d as the input. v is a linear control term and w is a robustness term. In (15), K is defined as:

$$K = \beta [\hat{F} + \eta] + (\beta + 1)|\hat{u}| \quad (16)$$

with $\hat{u} = -\bar{H}_a + v$ and $\Phi = \epsilon\lambda$. In (16), β is known as the gain margin of the design and represents the error in \bar{L}_a ; \hat{F} is the estimation error in \bar{H}_a . β and \hat{F} are evaluated by determining upper and lower bounds to the

errors on \bar{L}_a and \bar{H}_a . They are defined as: $\beta = \sqrt{\frac{\bar{L}_u}{\bar{L}_l}}$

and $\hat{F} = |\bar{H}_u - \bar{H}_l|$, where \bar{L}_u and \bar{H}_u , and \bar{L}_l and \bar{H}_l are the upper and lower bounds, respectively. To define these bounds we used the model in (11) with different scaling factors such that the responses of the simplified and enhanced models were contained between the bounds. Table 3 presents the scaling factors for the error bound models.

To reduce the noise effects of the simple numerical implementation of second-order derivatives, a second-order lowpass filter was added at the input of the sliding controller to smooth out the input trajectory. Of course, several other approaches could have been used. The cutoff frequency of the lowpass filter was set at 1 Hz with a damping ratio of 0.7. The other controller parameters were set to: $\lambda = 20$ rad/s, $\epsilon = 1^\circ = 0.017$ rad, and $\eta = 1$.

Fig. 4 shows a partial phase portrait of the state variables of the pendulum (position and speed) when the

Table 3: Scaling Factors for Error Bound Models

Parameter	Value	Parameter	Value
dA _u	1.25	dA _l	1.60
dB _u	1.00	dB _l	1.00
dC _u	0.00	dC _l	0.00
dD _u	1.00	dD _l	1.00
dE _u	0.90	dE _l	0.98
dF _u	1.30	dF _l	0.85
dG _u	1.30	dG _l	0.80
dL _u	0.90	dL _l	0.90

initial arm speed is 0 rad/s. The plot shows the response of the pendulum when moving toward the origin. Fig. 4 defines a region of attraction of the origin, which is important when switching from the swing-up to the positioning controller.

Fig. 4: Partial Phase Portrait for Pendulum State Variables: Initial Arm Speed = 0 rad/s

Fig. 5 shows an example of the trajectory tracking capabilities of the pendulum controller. The desired trajectory is a 25-degree sine wave with a 0.5 Hz frequency. Note that tracking is good, except for the delay which is introduced by the lowpass filter at the input to the controller.

Fig. 5: Trajectory Tracking Example for Pendulum Controller

Arm Controller

The reason for adding an arm controller is because the pendulum controller by itself cannot control the arm. For example, if the desired pendulum position is 0 degrees, the result will be a drift in the arm position even after the pendulum has reached the desired position.

The arm controller works by specifying a desired pendulum trajectory such that the desired arm response is achieved (see Fig. 3). The derivation of the arm control law follows.

First assume that (13) results in an exact cancellation of the nonlinear terms in the pendulum dynamics. Also,

assume that the pendulum controller is capable of perfect regulation (i.e., $\ddot{\phi}=0$). Substituting (13) into (11), with $w=0$ and $v = \ddot{\phi}_{des}$, results in:

$$\ddot{\phi} = v = \ddot{\phi}_{des}$$

Next, substitute (13) into (12). The result is:

$$\ddot{\theta} = -\left[\frac{F_a + G_a}{D_a}\right] - \left[\frac{E_a}{D_a}\right]v \quad (17)$$

Because of the effect of the lowpass filter on the pendulum controller, it is reasonable to assume that the pendulum acceleration will be small (i.e., $\ddot{\phi} = v = \ddot{\phi}_{des} \approx 0$). So, the second term on (15) can be dropped. The result is:

$$\ddot{\theta} = \left[\frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{L_1}{L_2} \right) (\dot{\theta})^2 + \left(\frac{g}{L_1} \right) \right] \phi \quad (18)$$

Now, assume that we would like the arm controller to be a PID. The desired arm dynamics are given by:

$$\ddot{\theta} = -K_1\dot{\tilde{\theta}} - K_2\tilde{\theta} - K_3\int_0^t \tilde{\theta} dt \quad (19)$$

where $\tilde{\theta} = \theta - \theta_{des}$ is the arm tracking error. Combining (18) and (19), the arm control law is:

$$\phi_{des} = \frac{-K_1\dot{\tilde{\theta}} - K_2\tilde{\theta} - K_3\int_0^t \tilde{\theta} dt}{\left[\frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{L_1}{L_2} \right) (\dot{\theta})^2 + \left(\frac{g}{L_1} \right) \right]}$$

The PID gains were chosen as: $K_1=2.5$, $K_2=2.0$, and $K_3=0.10$. Fig. 6 shows the response of the control system to steps on the desired arm position. Arm control is reasonably good and, as the figure shows, the system can follow desired arm trajectories for the full 360 degrees of the arm position. Fig. 7 shows the response to a ramp on the desired arm position. This figure better reflects the tracking accuracy of the system. Tracking is excellent during the ramp portion of the trajectory. Note that at the end of the ramp the system overshoots by approximately 20 degrees, but there are no large oscillations.

Swing-Up Control

A simple control approach to swing the pendulum from the downward position up to within the region of attraction of the positioning controller is by direct control of the arm acceleration. As mentioned in Section 2, the arm acceleration interacts with the pendulum dynamics through the coupling factor D . If it were possible to continuously increase the pendulum speed such that when it crossed the horizontal position it had sufficient speed to reach the region of attraction of the positioning controller, then swing-up would be accomplished.

Consider equation (3) in the range $90^\circ < |\phi| \leq 180^\circ$ and ignore \bar{H} at first. The result is $\ddot{\phi} = \bar{L}\tau$. We are looking for a destabilizing control law, i.e., a control law

Fig. 6: Control System Response to Various Step Inputs on the Desired Arm Position

Fig. 7: Control System Response to Ramp Input on the Desired Arm Position

that continuously increases the pendulum speed. One of such control laws is:

$$\tau = T_0 \text{sign}(\dot{\phi}) \quad (20)$$

where T_0 is a constant. Because of the effect of gravity and the centrifugal force due to the arm speed (i.e., the terms in \bar{H}) and also the pendulum position dependence of the coupling factor D , (20) will not necessarily result in a continuously increasing pendulum speed, but rather an oscillation with continuously increasing amplitude. This control law is a simplified version of the swing-up control law in [4].

To use (20), it is necessary to first set the pendulum into motion by applying a small input torque and then switch to (18) to induce the position oscillation. Also, T_0 must be chosen such that the pendulum has enough speed to reach the region of attraction of the positioning controller.

Fig. 8 shows the response of the system during swing-up. The initial torque for setting the pendulum into motion was arbitrarily chosen as two pulses of equal magnitude (1 N-m) and opposite polarity. The swing-up torque T_0 was set to 8.5 N-m. The positioning controller is activated when $|\phi|=45^\circ$ and at first there is a large control input transient generated by the pendulum controller as it accelerates the pendulum to bring it to the upward position. Stabilization of the arm is accomplished after the system has stabilized the pendulum position.

4. Implementation

The last step was to implement the system in the laboratory. The controller was discretized using simple techniques since the main objective was to see whether the controller would actually work with a real plant.

Fig. 8: Response of the System During Swing-Up:

Backward differences, the right-side rule and bilinear transformations were used to implement the derivatives, integrals, and filters, respectively. Although some tuning of the controller was required, the results obtained in the laboratory were similar to those in the simulations. Fig. 9 shows a swing-up sequence as seen in the laboratory. Note that this sequence is for the same case as the simulation plots in Fig. 8. Regulation was very good. Also, the response to steps in the desired arm position was fast, with the overshoot increasing to 30° for steps of 320° .

5. Conclusions

This paper presents the design of a modular nonlinear controller for swing-up and positioning of an inverted pendulum plant. The control system exhibits a large range of operation in the arm and pendulum positions. This is taken advantage of by introducing a simple technique to achieve pendulum swing-up. The system can control the position of the pendulum to follow desired trajectories. It also is capable of following desired trajectories in the arm position while maintaining control over the pendulum. The controller is easy to tune and test. Because of the control structure chosen, the system inherently prioritizes the control of the pendulum over the control of the arm. This means that when affected by disturbances the controller will first try to recover control

Fig. 9: Swing-Up Sequence as Seen in the Laboratory

over the pendulum, and then it will move the arm to the desired position.

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7. References

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